

Innovative Application of Dermofat Graft in Secondary Surgical Treatment of Cleft Lip: A Clinical Case Report

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Background: Cleft lip and palate (CL/P) is a common congenital craniofacial anomaly that requires gradual management from infancy. Although primary measures such as labioplasty and palatoplasty can resolve the initial defect, secondary deformities such as lip coloboma, short columella, and disproportionate nasal contour often remain. Autologous dermofat graft is now an alternative to soft tissue augmentation with promising results.

Case: An 8-year-old boy with a history of bilateral CL/P who had undergone labioplasty (2017), palatoplasty (2018), and alveolar bone graft (2023-2024), presented with complaints of asymmetrical lip and nasal shape. Examination revealed bilateral lip coloboma, nasal dorsum defect, and thickened postoperative scars. The patient was in good systemic condition and fit for surgery.

Methods: Secondary correction procedures of re-labioplasty, Mulliken technique primary rhinoplasty, columella lengthening, and dermofat graft augmentation from the right gluteal fold were performed. The graft was fixed to the nasal dorsum and lip, with a reverse-U incision design and layered suturing. The patient received structured postoperative care and family education.

Discussion: The use of dermofat graft has been shown to be safe and effective in improving soft tissue volume in CL/P patients. The literature supports the effectiveness of this technique in improving lip and nasal contours, with minimal complications. This approach is also relevant for regional hospitals with limited resources.

Conclusion: The application of dermofat graft as part of secondary correction of CL/P shows satisfactory aesthetic results, without major complications, and can be a viable alternative in soft tissue-based craniofacial reconstructive surgery.

Published On:
29 April 2026

KEYWORDS: Cleft lip and palate, dermofat graft, reconstructive surgery, labioplasty, secondary rhinoplasty

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

I. INTRODUCTION

Cleft lip and/or palate (CL/P) is one of the most common craniofacial congenital anomalies globally. It results from failure of tissue fusion during the embryogenesis phase between the 4th to 12th week of pregnancy. CL/P may stand alone or be part of a specific genetic syndrome. This disorder not only causes aesthetic problems, but also affects the patient's speech, eating, psychosocial functions and overall quality of life (Alighieri et al., 2020).

Globally, the incidence of CL/P ranges from 1.00 to 1.67 per 1,000 live births. The Asian region has the highest

incidence, with an incidence of approximately 1 in 600 to 700 live births. Studies in Japan showed an incidence of 1.46 per 1,000 births, and a meta-analysis in China (1986-2015) recorded a rate of 1.4 per 1,000 births (Haas Junior et al., 2023). In Indonesia, based on Riskesdas data, there was an increase in prevalence from 0.08% in 2013 to 0.12% in 2018. A study in Bandung during the period 2011-2015 recorded 1,596 cases of CL/P, with the proportion of CL+P types totaling 60.9%, CL alone 20.3%, and CP alone 18.8% (Zheng et al., 2020).

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In Bali Province, specific epidemiologic data on CL/P is still limited. However, based on data from Bali Mandara Regional Hospital from 2023 to 2025, there were 40 cases of patients with CL/P. This number may not fully reflect the reality, as limited access to health services, especially in rural areas, leads to underreporting and delayed diagnosis.

Treatment of CL/P is multidisciplinary and stepwise, starting from infancy to adolescence. However, primary surgeries such as labioplasty and palatoplasty often leave residual deformities that require further correction. Secondary problems such as lip coloboma, columella retraction, nasal asymmetry and disproportionate lip contour are common complaints after primary surgery (Goich & Schachter, 2023). Innovation in CL/P reconstructive surgery is now leading to the use of soft tissue grafts such as autologous dermofat. Dermofat graft has the advantages of high biocompatibility, ability to fill soft tissue defects naturally, and low donor site morbidity. It is ideal for improving lip and nasal dorsum contours, especially in patients with complex secondary deformities. This technique is also considered effective in improving aesthetic results and patient satisfaction without the need for additional bone or cartilage sources (Chung et al., 2022). This case is important to report as it illustrates the comprehensive application of dermofat graft as part of a combination of secondary surgery in a patient with a history of bilateral CL/P. This approach has the potential to be an efficient, effective and affordable surgical solution in improving the quality of life of CL/P patients, especially in areas with limited access to advanced craniofacial surgery facilities such as Bali.

An 8-year-old boy came to RSUD Bali Mandara with complaints of asymmetrical lip and nose shape and prominent surgical scars. The patient had a history of bilateral cleft lip and palate that had been treated at an early age through several surgical stages, including primary labioplasty (2017), palatoplasty (2018), and alveolar bone graft in 2023 and 2024. Despite the primary surgery, there were still abnormalities such as bilateral lip coloboma, short columella, flat nasal dorsum, and thickened post-surgical scars. These abnormalities cause significant aesthetic disturbance and risk compromising the child's self-confidence as they age.

The patient was in good general condition, actively attending 3rd grade school, with no functional complaints such as pain, feeding difficulties, or airway infections. Physical examination revealed asymmetrical nasal flare, short columella, defects in the nasal contour and lips, and intraoral scars.

Objective: Nostril width ratio and Columellar angle of the patient
Figure 1. The nostril width ratio and the angle of columella from sagittal plane. These two simple measures are useful as independent and objective indicator of presurgical severity of cleft lip nasal deformity

Objective: nasal form (NF 3)

Objective: nasal symmetry (NS 3)

Objective: vermilion border (VB 3) Objective: nasolabial profile (NLP 3)

Figure 2. The patient's clinical condition in August 2024, following labioplasty, palatoplasty, and alveolar bone graft procedures performed between 2017 to 2024. Kujipers-jagtman reference photographs used for rating the nasolabial area in cleft lips. Nasal form, nasal symmetry, vermilion border, and the nasolabial profile are each rated on the ordinal scale described by Asher-McDade et. al, where 1 = very good appearance, 2 = good appearance, 3 = fair appearance, 4 poor appearance, 5 = very poor appearance.

To objectively evaluate the clinical progression and the efficacy of the secondary interventions, the Kujipers–Jagtman (KJ) scoring system was implemented. This validated aesthetic index utilizes a 5-point scale (1: very good/normal; 5: very poor) across five distinct anatomical parameters. As of August 2024, the patient's clinical condition was as follows: Nasal Form 3 because the right side of the nose is slightly flatter than the left. For Nasal Symmetry, a score of 3 was given because the nostrils are not the same size. The right nostril looks wider and its base

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is a little lower than the left nostril. For the Vermilion Border, which has a score of 2, the repair is very good, but you can still see a slight notch or small break along the lip line in the damaged area. Finally, the nasolabial profile received a score of 3 because, when viewed from the side, the nasal tip is quite visible, though slightly less prominent on the affected side. The shape of the upper and lower lips appears harmonious but lacks fullness.

Objective: nasal form (NF 3)

Objective: nasal symmetry (NS 3)

Objective: vermilion border (VB 2)

Objective: nasolabial profile (NLP 2)

Figure 3. The patient's clinical condition in June 2025, 9 months post-operative revision alveolar bone graft and planned re-labialplasty + primary rhinoplasty using the Mulliken technique.

The Kuijpers–Jagtman scoring system was applied to objectively evaluate the patient's nasolabial appearance prior to secondary surgery. The assessment revealed several residual deformities. The nasal form received a score of 3, indicating marked asymmetry with a flat dorsum and alar base deviation. The nasal tip and columella length were also rated 3, reflecting a shortened columella with poor projection. Evaluation of the vermilion border showed mild irregularity, scoring 3. The overall nasolabial profile was judged disharmonious, with a deficient nasal projection, and was assigned a score of 2. However, the upper lip symmetry was severely compromised, with a score of 2 due to the presence of bilateral coloboma and evident asymmetry. These findings highlight the patient's substantial aesthetic deficits and strongly support the indication for secondary reconstructive procedures, including re-labioplasty, primary rhinoplasty with columella lengthening, and dermofat graft augmentation.

The patient underwent secondary reconstructive procedures of bilateral re-labioplasty, primary rhinoplasty using the Mulliken technique, lengthening of the columella, and placement of a dermofat graft from the right gluteal fold fixed to the nasal dorsum and lips. The patient was prepared

to undergo surgical correction secondary to residual lip and nose deformities post bilateral cleft lip and palate surgery. Stages began with a thorough evaluation with results showing the patient in good systemic condition, with ASA I anesthesia status and general anesthesia (GA) technique using an orotracheal tube. The patient was positioned supine with a head ring. The procedure began with cleaning and disinfection of the face and right gluteal area as the donor site. The incision design used a combination approach of Mulliken's re-labioplasty and primary rhinoplasty techniques. For correction of the nasal deformity, a Tajima reverse U incision was performed in the columella and nasal dome region. Dissection was continued to release the perinasal tissue and improve the nasal cartilage structure. The deviated septum was repositioned and stabilized to the midline using absorbable sutures. The dilated ala nasi was also repositioned in a medial-inferior direction.

Figure 4. Secondary reconstruction in the form of bilateral re-labioplasty, primary rhinoplasty using the Mulliken technique, lengthening of the columella, and installation of dermofat.

Next, autologous dermofat was taken from the right gluteal fold. The dermofat was then shaped to the required contour and strategically placed on the nasal dorsum and lip vermilion area. The graft was fixed to the surrounding tissue with absorbable monofilament sutures to ensure stable and symmetrical positioning. In the re-labioplasty stage, incisions are made at the supralabial and coloboma. Area de-epithelialization, subperiosteal dissection, and medial tissue mobilization are performed to restore the natural shape of the lip. Adjustment of the vermilion was done with Z-plasty technique and insertion of dermofat graft to improve lip volume and projection. Sutures were layered up to the intraoral mucosa. The patient was also provided with education to the family on how to care for the wound, clean the nasal stent, and the importance of maintaining hygiene and early mobilization. All of these steps were performed in a multidisciplinary manner by a team of plastic surgeons, anesthesiologists, and wound nurses at RSUD Bali Mandara. This method illustrates a comprehensive approach that combines surgical techniques, the use of autologous tissue, and a structured post-operative care protocol to ensure optimal reconstructive outcomes both functionally and aesthetically.

Figure 5. The patient's clinical condition in January 2026, 6 months after surgery re-labioplasty + primary rhinoplasty using the Muliken technique.

The assessment conducted in January 2026, representing the six-month post-operative milestone, demonstrated a definitive shift in the patient's aesthetic profile, with the total Kuijpers–Jagtman (KJ) score improving to an optimized value. This score signifies a "Very Good" outcome, nearing the anatomical norms of a non-cleft population. The transition of both nasal form and symmetry to a score of 2 reflects the successful structural reorganization achieved through definitive rhinoplasty and columella lengthening. By 6 months post-operatively, the resolution of surgical edema allowed for the visualization of a more defined nasal tip and improved alar base parity. The columella, previously short and retracted, exhibited stable projection, providing better support to the nasal apex. The most striking improvement was observed in the vermilion border, which achieved a perfect score of 1. This indicates a seamless continuity of the mucocutaneous junction. The re-labioplasty, combined with the underlying muscle repositioning, effectively eliminated the previous "whistle deformity" or notch, restoring a natural and symmetrical Cupid's bow. Optimization of nasal and lip profiles reached the highest possible aesthetic rating (Score: 1), this is directly attributable to the dermofat graft augmentation. At 6 months, the graft had undergone successful neovascularization and integration, providing sustained volume to the philtrum and nasal base. This volumization corrected the previous midface retrusion, creating a harmonious sagittal relationship between the nose, upper lip, and chin.

II. DISCUSSION

Management of secondary deformities in patients with cleft lip and palate (CL/P) remains a major challenge in craniofacial surgery, especially when facing aesthetic residues such as lip coloboma, short columella, flat nasal dorsum, and asymmetrical soft tissues. Although primary surgeries such as labioplasty and palatoplasty aim to correct the underlying structures, long-term results often leave facial imbalances that require further intervention (Chung et al., 2022; Haas Junior et al., 2023).

The principal deformities encountered in bilateral cleft lip include: (1) a protruded or deviated premaxilla relative to the retruded lateral maxillary segments, (2) wide or asymmetric alveolar gaps, and (3) a shortened columella accompanied by excessive nasal width. Attempting to approximate the orbicularis oris muscle anterior to the protruding premaxilla can increase the likelihood of wound dehiscence and imposes undue tension on both the premaxilla and maxilla, potentially resulting in maxillary retrusion or rotation of the premaxilla. In the absence of nasolabial molding (NAM), the nasal appearance following primary lip repair in bilateral cleft lip patients is often characterized by a broad, flattened nose with inverted nostril axes and a widened nasal tip. These features are primarily the consequence of columella shortening and the skeletal imbalance between the premaxilla and lateral maxillary segments (Mackay, Samson, & Henry, 2017).

In this case, a combination of re-labioplasty, rhinoplasty, columella lengthening, and soft tissue augmentation using dermofat graft was a strategic choice to achieve maximum aesthetic correction. This technique has a strong scientific basis. According to Chung et al. (2022), the use of dermofat graft in CL/P patients successfully increased vermilion volume and resulted in a more natural lip contour without significant complications such as high tissue reabsorption or other secondary deformities. Dermofat also provides advantages in terms of tissue integration, as it comes from an autologous source with minimal risk of rejection or infection.

Haas Junior et al. (2023) in a systematic review stated that fat grafting including dermofat is effective in improving vertical lip dimensions, lip projection, as well as facial symmetry. The increase in lip volume significantly contributes to patients' aesthetic and functional satisfaction. This technique also has less morbidity compared to the use of cartilage or bone graft, which requires bone manipulation and additional donor sites. In addition, a study by Goich and Schachter (2023) showed that autologous fat grafting—both in the form of microsurgery and dermofat is a rapidly growing approach in secondary CL/P correction. This technique offers the advantages of contour flexibility, high biocompatibility, and repeatability when necessary.

The uniqueness of this case lies in the combinative application of dermofat graft in one surgical session alongside re-labioplasty and primary rhinoplasty. This

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approach is relatively rarely reported simultaneously in the local literature in Indonesia. This technique not only aims to improve soft tissue contour and volume but also supports reconstruction of nasal architecture through cartilage repositioning and columella lengthening. With the reverse-U (Tajima) incision design, the surgery can achieve symmetrical and harmonious results to the patient's overall face.

The clinical implications of this approach are significant, especially in Indonesia, where access to advanced craniofacial surgery is limited. The study by Khan et al. (2024) compared dermofat with bone graft for maxillary augmentation and concluded that dermofat provided similar results with lower complications and faster recovery time. This is a feasible and practical solution, especially in regional hospitals such as RSUD Bali Mandara.

Furthermore, an individualized approach such as in this case-taking into account the patient's aesthetic needs and previous surgical history-demonstrates the importance of personalized and holistic treatment planning. The use of dermofat graft not only fulfills the goal of anatomical correction, but also impacts the psychosocial aspects of the growing pediatric patient, especially in building self-confidence and social acceptance.

CONCLUSIONS AND LIMITATION

The application of dermofat graft as part of a secondary correction procedure in a patient with bilateral cleft lip and palate (CL/P) showed significant results both aesthetically and functionally. In this case, the combination of dermofat graft with re-labioplasty, primary rhinoplasty, and columella lengthening resulted in a more harmonious lip and nose contour, improved dorsum nasal projection, and optimized facial symmetry.

The longitudinal application of the Kuijpers–Jagtman (KJ) scoring system proved to be an indispensable tool for objective outcome measurement. The significant reduction in the patient's total KJ score from fair to very good over a 17-month period provides quantifiable evidence of the procedural efficacy. Specifically, the dermofat graft offered a reliable, biocompatible solution for augmenting the philtral and nasal base regions, areas that often remain deficient after conventional secondary repairs.

The dermofat graft technique has proven to be effective and safe as it uses autologous tissue with minimal risk of complications, as well as high biocompatibility and low donor site morbidity. This approach is also flexible as it can be combined with other reconstructive techniques in one procedure, thus minimizing the number of surgeries and speeding up the recovery process. In addition, the successful application of this technique provides important educational value for the advanced practice of CL/P reconstructive surgery, especially in centers with limited facilities such as regional hospitals. An individualized approach and

personalized therapy are key to success, given the variation in primary postoperative deformity in each patient.

In conclusion, the integration of objective scoring systems into clinical practice, as demonstrated in this report, facilitates a data-driven approach to cleft care. The synergistic use of dermofat grafting and definitive rhinoplasty not only restores anatomical symmetry but also significantly minimizes the visible stigma of the cleft deformity. Thus, this technique deserves to be considered as one of the standards in the management of CL/P secondary deformities in Indonesia, and has the potential to improve patients' quality of life and self-confidence.

Despite the significant aesthetic improvements observed in this case, several limitations must be considered: As a single-case report. While the results are promising, they cannot be generalized to the broader population of patients with bilateral cleft lip and palate without larger, prospective cohort studies or randomized controlled trials. Second, follow-up duration which the current assessment concludes at six months post-operatively. And subjectivity of assessment (Kuijpers–Jagtman scoring system) is a validated and reliable tool, it remains a qualitative visual assessment.

ETHICS APPROVAL

Informed consent has been acquired from the patient. The patient written informed consent to be published as a case report.

COMPLETING INTERESTS

All the authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest

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